

THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF WOMEN'S FOOTBALL

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Аннотация. В статье автором проведен теоретический анализ развития и становления женского футбола в историческом аспекте в Узбекистане и за рубежом, а также выявлены перспективы и тенденции развития современного женского футбола в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: футбол, женский футбол, футбольные клубы, ФИФА, чемпионат Узбекистана, кубок Узбекистана.

Annotation. The article presents the theoretical analysis of the development and formation of women's football in the historical aspect in Uzbekistan and abroad, as well as the prospects and trends of development of modern football in the Uzbekistan.

Keywords: football, women's football, football clubs, FIFA, RFU, Uzbekistan championship, Uzbekistan Cup.

The most common sport in the world is football. Football is one of the most important strategic resources for the development of a full – fledged and healthy society and an individual who not only depends on the social system, but also actively influences various aspects and spheres of public life-political, economic, cultural. The purpose of the study is to summarize the historical aspects of the formation and development of women's football in Uzbekistan and foreign countries, to analyze current trends in the development of women's football in Uzbekistan. To solve the tasks set, the study used theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological sources on the research issue. Scientists have conducted a large number of scientific studies in the field of professional football. Research activities in men's football have a long history, which allowed us to accumulate extensive material.

But a very small part of them belongs to the study of the history of the formation of women's football. Defended dissertations^{1,2}are devoted to relatively narrow problems of improving the skills of female football players. In the scientific literature¹, there are not so many studies devoted exclusively to the history of the formation of women's football. At the same time, the importance of periodization of the history of the development and formation of women's football as a process is determined by the need to identify common patterns and specific differences in different historical epochs related to events taking place both in the surrounding world and within society.

The historical aspects of the development and formation of women's football in the world begin in ancient times and are not inferior in duration to men's football. The origin of the first women's football team dates back to 1895, in England. At this time, the first women's

¹ Колясова Р.Р. «Педагогическая модель скоростно-силовой подготовки футболисток 17-18 лет в спортивном отделении вуза»

² Чувва В. А. «Гипоксические и релаксационные средства тренировочных воздействий в подготовке футболисток»

football club was organized and the first match among women's teams was held. The earliest references to international matches date back to the early 1880s: these were meetings between English and Scottish women's teams. Throughout its historical development, women's football has felt discriminated against by men. World War II was a powerful impetus for the development of women's football.

At this time, in England, so-called "workers'" teams began to be created in factories and factories. The popularity of women's football was growing. After the First World War, women's football was discriminated against. Already in 1920, women's football reached a new level of fame. January 30, 1921-English football officials take another step towards banning women from big-time sports. The English Football Association additionally announced in a special resolution that "football is absolutely not suitable for the weaker sex", and banned clubs from issuing permits for organizing women's football teams. The banning order of 1921 was one of a large number of examples of the English Association's penchant for banning women's football. FIFA's attitude towards women's football was similar. In the late 60s, with the growth of feminist movements in the world, there were qualitative changes in the history of women's football.

New life principles, increasing the role of women in society, led to a rapid revival of women's football in Norway, Sweden and Germany, where real professional football clubs began to appear instead of factory amateur clubs. It was these countries that asked FIFA to organize the Women's World Cup. In Russia, women started playing football at the beginning of the 20th century. In the Russian Sport magazine in 1910, it was written: "The significance of football is disputed by many. A special feature is the fact that this sport is only for men. Not to mention the fact that women's legs are usually heavier, shorter and weaker than men's, the former do not have the necessary speed of movement and agility when playing football."

In Soviet times, women's football existed in a semi-legal position. As in Europe, interest in it emerged in the 1960s and 1970s. And in 1972, the USSR State Committee for Sports imposed a ban on "men's" sports, including women's football, referring to their harmfulness to the female body. The ban was lifted only in perestroika times. The year of birth of football in Uzbekistan is considered 1912 to be 1912, as it was then that football teams were created in Ferghana and Kokand, a little later in Andijan, Tashkent and Samarkand, and long-distance matches were held. The highest League of the Uzbekistan Women's Football Championship is the highest division of the championship Uzbekistan, where the strongest women's clubs of the country play. Women's football in Uzbekistan, although young, is rapidly developing. Since the mid-2000s, when the first women's teams were formed, the sport has undergone many changes. The development and introduction of women's football in the country is due to the efforts of the Football Association and its partners.

Professional women's football clubs in Uzbekistan play a significant role in the development of women's football in the country. Among the most famous clubs worth noting:

- "Sevinch"
- «Bunyodkor»
- "Pakhtakor"

These clubs were founded at different times, but all of them significantly contributed to the promotion of women's football in Uzbekistan.

Tournaments have been held since 1995. Since 2010, it has been held under the auspices of the Women's Football Association of Uzbekistan (AJFU) under the Football Federation of Uzbekistan (now AFU-Football Association of Uzbekistan).

Since the 2013 season, only professional clubs are allowed to participate in the Top League.

Since 2011, the Championship of Uzbekistan among the First League teams has been held. The number of participants is not constant. In addition to professional clubs, physical therapy and KFC are allowed to participate in absolute compliance with the Regulations.

The exchange between the leagues is stipulated by the Regulations and is carried out according to the sports principle. In the First League, the team that took the 10th (last) place in the Highest League is eliminated. The winner of the First League goes to the Top League.

If the First League clubs refuse to participate in the national championship in the Top League, it is allowed to retain a place in the top division for those teams that were supposed to be eliminated from the Top League.

After the AZFU was abolished from the 2018 season, the tournament was held by the PFL of Uzbekistan (under the control of the AFU) until 2022 inclusive, which also controlled the women's national championship in the First League and the U-16 youth championship. Since the 2023 season, the championship of Uzbekistan and the championship in the I League, as well as the U-16 youth championship, are held under the auspices of the AFU.

According to V. N. Khan, "Uzbek women's football needs to complete a normal (correct) pyramid with a strong foundation, which will be based on mass participation, a large number of people involved in the game and playing football." Thus, we can identify a number of factors that limit the development of women's football in Uzbekistan: weak material and technical base and infrastructure of most regional federations and clubs, insufficient equipment, equipment, simulators, qualified coaches, insufficient staffing of football, insufficient involvement of the population in regular physical education and sports.

The analysis and generalization of data from the national literature made it possible to establish the main trends in the development and formation of women's football in our country: at the federal level: – implementation of the law "On Physical Culture and Sports in Uzbekistan" and the current "Football Development Program – 2020;

– providing scientific, methodological, financial, logistical, informational and analytical assistance to regional women's football federations;

– improving the social status of women's football in the country and individual regions; at the regional level:

– development and implementation of programs for the development of women's football in the regions;

– implementation of a personnel policy aimed at improving the skills of specialists in the field of women's football; at the municipal level:

– popularization of women's football, increasing the mass popularity of women's football;

– development of women's football in the system of primary, secondary and higher education, involvement of the adult population in women's football;

– strengthening the resource potential of women's football clubs.

The identified trends in the development of women's football depend on the ongoing transformations in modern society, the socio-economic situation and the legislative framework.

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